

Efficacy and Effectiveness of Antipsychotics in Schizophrenia: Network Meta-Analyses Combining Evidence from Randomised Controlled Trials and Real-World Data

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Abstract

Background: There is debate about the generalisability of results from randomised clinical trials (RCTs) to ‘real-world’ (RW) settings. Studying outcomes of treatments for schizophrenia can shed light on this issue and inform treatment guidelines. We therefore compared the efficacy (RCT) and effectiveness (RW) of antipsychotics for relapse prevention in schizophrenia and estimated overall treatment effects utilizing all available RCT and RW evidence.

Methods: We conducted network meta-analyses (NMAs) using individual participant data from Swedish and Finnish national registries and aggregate data from RCTs. The target population was people with schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder with stabilized symptoms. We analysed each registry separately to obtain hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% Confidence Interval (CI) for relapse within 6 months post-antipsychotic initiation as our main outcome. Interventions were antipsychotics, no antipsychotic use, and placebo. We compared HRs vs a reference drug (oral haloperidol) between registries, and between registry individuals who would be eligible and ineligible for RCTs, using the ratio of HRs (RHR). We synthesized evidence using NMA and compared results from our RW-NMA with our RCT-NMA, including oral vs long-acting injectable (LAI) formulations. Finally, we conducted a joint RW/RCT-NMA.

Findings: We included 90,469 individuals from the Swedish and Finnish registries (mean age 45·9 (SD 14·6) years; of whom N=43,025 (48%) were women) and 10,091 individuals from 30 RCTs (mean age 39·6 years (SD 11·7); N=3,724 (36·9%) women). Ethnicity data were unavailable in the registries. We found good agreement in effectiveness of antipsychotics between Swedish and Finnish registries (RHR 0·97, 95%CI [0·88; 1·08]). Drug effectiveness vs no antipsychotic was larger in RCT-eligible than RCT-ineligible individuals (RHR 1·40 [1·24; 1·59]). Efficacy vs

placebo in RCTs was larger than effectiveness vs no antipsychotic in RW (RHR 2·58 [2·02; 3·30]). We found no evidence of differences between effectiveness and efficacy for between-drug comparisons (RHR vs haloperidol oral 1·17 [0·83; 1·65], where RHR>1 means superior effectiveness in RW to RCTs), except for LAI vs oral comparisons (RHR 0·73 [0·53; 0·99], indicating superior effectiveness in RW relative to RCTs). The RW-NMA showed clozapine was most effective, followed by olanzapine LAI. The RCT-NMA exhibited heterogeneity and inconsistency. The RW/RCT-NMA identified olanzapine as the most efficacious antipsychotic amongst those present in both RCTs and RW.

Interpretation: LAI antipsychotics perform slightly better in RW than according to RCTs.

Otherwise, RCT evidence was in line with RW evidence for most between-drug comparisons, but RCTs may overestimate effectiveness of antipsychotics observed in routine care settings. Our results further the understanding of the generalisability of RCT findings to clinical practice and may inform preferential prescribing guidelines.

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Introduction

Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) are the best source of evidence to estimate relative treatment effects.¹ For some interventions, e.g. statins, effects estimated in RCTs are largely consistent across settings.² Such agreement occurs when factors that interact with treatment are minimal. However, this scenario may not apply to some interventions, especially in mental health, where multiple context-related variables may vary between RCTs and real-world practice, leading to different estimates of clinical outcomes and thus giving rise to an ‘efficacy-effectiveness’ gap.³ In the mental health field, a factor that may further increase such an efficacy-effectiveness gap is our recent finding that up to 80% of individuals with schizophrenia are ineligible to participate in RCTs, meaning that populations in RCTs are not entirely representative of real-world populations.⁴

Network meta-analysis constitutes a powerful method to synthesise comparative evidence when multiple treatment options are available for the same condition.⁵ The latter applies to schizophrenia.⁶ Furthermore, we chose the approach of an NMA since pharmaceutical companies do not prioritize studies on the comparative efficacy between treatments.⁷ For instance, esketamine was approved for treatment-resistant depression in 2019 by the FDA based on placebo-controlled trials, despite the availability of another approved treatment option for this indication.⁸ Another example from the field of mental health is brexpiprazole, which was approved for schizophrenia by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) based on four RCTs, three of which were placebo-controlled. The only active-comparator RCT used quetiapine as control, although, according to the EMA, aripiprazole would have been a more appropriate comparator.⁹ Industry-sponsored studies are not of lower methodological rigor.¹⁰ However, they may sometimes favour the sponsored intervention when comparators with inferior benefit or harm profile are selected.¹¹

Some observational studies have provided conflicting results about the effects of antipsychotics for maintenance treatment in schizophrenia.¹²⁻¹⁴ In recent years, however, the improved quality and increased availability of real-world (RW) and RCT data have facilitated large-scale use of such data in research.¹⁵ A combined analysis of RCT and RW data may thus increase statistical power to detect differences between active treatments and help identify best-performing drugs for relapse prevention across RW and RCT settings.¹⁶ Moreover, NMA may overcome the limitation of the aforementioned scarcity of active drug comparators in RCTs done for schizophrenia to date. Although some researchers have combined RCTs and observational studies on long-acting injectable (LAI) antipsychotics in schizophrenia,¹⁷ we are unaware of NMAs pooling RCT and RW evidence of antipsychotic treatment effects for relapse prevention. We therefore synthesised RCT and RW evidence of relapse prevention effects of oral and LAI antipsychotics by applying NMA. Our goal was to inform clinical guidelines and routine care about relative effects of antipsychotics and the generalizability of RCT data to routine care of patients with schizophrenia.

Research in context

Evidence before this study

There is an ongoing debate about the generalizability of results from randomized clinical trials (RCTs) to real-world (RW) clinical settings. We have previously found that 80% of real-world patients with schizophrenia spectrum disorders are ineligible to participate in relapse-prevention antipsychotics RCTs, and that ineligible patients overall have worse outcomes than eligible patients with schizophrenia. We performed searches in PubMed on 5 July 2023 to retrieve possible studies integrating RCT and real-world evidence about antipsychotics. The search ‘real-world AND RCT AND antipsychotic AND network meta-analysis’ did not yield any results. The search ‘real-world AND RCT AND antipsychotic’ yielded no applicable studies to our study design, only either RCTs or real-world studies. We therefore set out to integrate RCT and real-world evidence and used individual patient data from national registries from Finland and Sweden and study-level information from 30 RCTs (as published by Schneider-Thoma and colleagues (2021), updated to March 2022), to compare antipsychotic drugs for individuals with schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder, using relapse as the primary outcome.

Added value of this study

We included over one hundred thousand individuals with schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder from Swedish and Finnish national registries and RCTs. By using two national registries and study-level information from the most comprehensive and up-to-date systematic review of RCTs, our work constitutes the largest meta-analysis of antipsychotic treatment effects and the first study synthesizing large-scale evidence from RW and RCT settings in psychiatry. We found that the advantage of long-acting injectable (LAI) antipsychotics compared to their oral counterpart is larger in RW than RCT settings, which was another ongoing debate in psychiatry. Furthermore, RCT evidence was in line with RW evidence for most between-drug comparisons. Finally, we found evidence that relative effects of antipsychotics vs. placebo estimated in RCTs may overestimate effects vs. no antipsychotic use in routine care settings.

Implications of all the available evidence

Our results may inform clinical treatment guidelines for schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder with regards to preferred treatment options for relapse prevention when considering efficacy/effectiveness as one measure. For example, based on our findings of superior effectiveness of olanzapine to haloperidol, patients may decide to try olanzapine if haloperidol insufficiently reduces their symptoms. In addition, LAI formulations of antipsychotics should be considered higher-up in updated clinical guidelines, as we showed they perform better in RW clinical settings to avoid relapse in schizophrenia than previously shown in RCTs. Furthermore, regarding future research avenues, our methodology and work lay the groundwork for future analyses integrating RCT and RW efficacy/effectiveness measures for additional psychiatric disorders.

Methods

Methods overview

In line with expert recommendations,¹⁸ we made the inclusion, treatment and time zero criteria as similar as possible across RW and RCTs (also see below). In Figure 1, we provide a graphical methods overview. First, we analysed two national registries separately and compared treatment effects between them. We also compared effects in registry individuals eligible for RCTs vs ineligible ones (as defined in our previous work and also described below).⁴ Then, we conducted NMA of registry data. Second, we estimated relative efficacies in an NMA of RCTs. Third, we compared both sources, thus examining a possible efficacy-effectiveness gap. Fourth, we performed a joint NMA of all evidence. Finally, we performed several sensitivity analyses. Following recommendations,^{19,20} we provide estimates and corresponding confidence intervals, avoiding the use of statistical significance to characterize results. The protocol of this study was published prior to analysis (<https://osf.io/q9prm/>). No amendments to the protocol were made; the only add-on includes two post-hoc analyses (described below).

Figure 1: Overview of methods. IPD: individual-patient level data. HR: hazard ratio. RHR: ratio of HR. NMA: network meta-analysis. RCT: randomized clinical trial. Green colours correspond to the analyses of registries; grey to those of RCTs; yellow to those of RW-RCT combined analyses.

Inclusion criteria in real-world studies and RCTs

The RW study population consisted of individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder in nationwide Swedish and Finnish registries, which included patients identified from inpatient, specialized outpatient care, sickness absence, and disability pension data. We included individuals who were likely to be symptomatically stable while on maintenance treatment with antipsychotics, in line with the design of RCTs on relapse prevention and similar to previous research.⁴ RW participants needed to fulfil the following inclusion criteria: (i) a diagnosis of schizophrenia (ICD-10 F20) or schizoaffective disorder (F25); (ii) currently on second-generation antipsychotic or haloperidol monotherapy; and (iii) stability of 12 weeks on antipsychotic monotherapy. Similar stability criteria were applied to antipsychotic non-use periods by people who had also been on monotherapy (as described above) since non-use was employed as reference exposure. The use of other first-generation antipsychotics as monotherapy has been reported to be

negligible in the Finnish and Swedish populations.²¹ Each patient could have multiple treatment periods of the same or different antipsychotics and non-use. Follow-up started after a 12-week stabilization period and ended at an outcome event (see below), a change in exposure status, death, or hospitalization due to other reasons than relapse, at the pre-defined follow-up period (6 and 12 months, see below) or at the end of data linkage. Follow-up extended until 31 December 2017 in the Finnish cohort and until 31 December 2018 in the Swedish cohort^{13,22} (details in Supplement, Section 1).

Regarding RCTs, we included the relapse-prevention studies from Schneider-Thoma et al²³ comparing second-generation antipsychotics to each other, haloperidol, or placebo after an updated search of this review on 6 March 2022 (Supplement, Section 2.1). Participants had schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder, with very few having related disorders (Supplement, Section 2.2). All were stabilized on antipsychotics (according to the authors' definitions).

Main Outcome

The primary outcome was relapse during 6 months. In RW studies, we defined relapse as hospital admission due to acute psychosis. In RCTs, we used the outcome “relapse” as defined by the authors of the RCTs as no substantial differences in treatment effects due to differences in relapse-definitions were observed in the original systematic review (see below for a sensitivity analysis using psychiatric hospitalisation as an outcome in RCTs).²³

Analysis of real-world data

In RW analyses, we analysed all periods of second-generation antipsychotics and haloperidol in monotherapy use and non-use periods of antipsychotics. Analyses were conducted with stratified,

within-individual Cox models to obtain Hazard Ratios (HRs). This method was chosen to minimise chances of confounding. We estimated HRs between all antipsychotics, and between antipsychotics and non-use of antipsychotics, separately in the two registries. Analyses were adjusted for time since cohort entry and for use of other psychotropic medications (Supplement, Section 1). Analyses were conducted in SAS 9.4. The end-product of this stage was one set of estimates per registry (HRs between all drugs, between drugs and non-use, and corresponding standard errors of logHRs).

Subsequently, we inspected the agreement between the registries in a scatterplot, plotting the estimated HRs and 95% Confidence Intervals (CIs) vs haloperidol oral, where $HR > 1$ favours haloperidol. To quantify agreement, we estimated the ratio of HRs (RHR) for each drug, i.e. HR from RW over HR from RCTs, where $RHR = 1$ refers to perfect agreement between registries for the effects vs haloperidol; $RHR > 1$ means $HR_{RW} > HR_{RCT}$. Then, we synthesized the drug-specific RHRs in a random-effects meta-analysis, using **meta**²⁴ in R.²⁵ We estimated the weighted Spearman rank correlation coefficient (ρ) for the two sets of HRs using **wcorr**,²⁶ with weights equal to the inverse of the variances of the RHRs, where $\rho = 1$ corresponding to identical ranking (according to the point estimates) in the two registries. To obtain a p-value against the null hypothesis of no correlation, we performed a permutation test (Supplement, section 3).

Next, we synthesized the results from the registries in a random-effects NMA.²⁷ We assumed a common heterogeneity parameter (τ) for all comparisons in the network, and ranked treatments using p-scores.²⁸ The main assumption of NMA is transitivity; we assessed this by looking at the distribution of possible effect modifiers across the registries. Consistency refers to the agreement between direct and indirect evidence, and we assessed it via a global (design-by-treatment test)²⁹ and a local method (back-calculation method).³⁰ We used the **netmeta** package.³¹

We explored differences between RCT-eligible and ineligible individuals, as defined in our previous publication.⁴ In brief, we applied the following exclusion criteria commonly used in modern RCTs of second-generation antipsychotics to RW individuals, to obtain RCT-eligible and ineligible individuals:⁴ age <18 or >65 years; history of substance abuse; history of suicide attempt; treatment resistance; serious somatic disease; mood stabilizer or antidepressant use; intellectual disability/mental retardation; tardive dyskinesia; and pregnancy or breastfeeding. More details are provided in the Supplement, Section 1, Subsection Eligibility vs. ineligibility to RCTs. Then, we repeated the RW analyses outlined in the previous paragraph for RCT-eligible and RCT-ineligible individuals separately; and compared estimates of effectiveness. Of note, eligibility criteria are known to vary across RCTs. Due to the necessary operationalisation of exclusion criteria by documented diagnoses in the registries, our RCT-eligibility criteria may be more restrictive than the eligibility criteria used in some RCTs (Supplement sections 1 and 2.5)⁴. The eligibility criteria we used likely reflect the practice of an explanatory, rather than a pragmatic trial.

In a first post-hoc analysis, we explored differences between LAI and oral formulations of antipsychotics, to quantify differences in effectiveness between formulations. Our hypothesis was that RW evidence shows larger benefit of LAI over counterpart oral formulations compared to RCTs,¹³ since individuals with poor adherence may be excluded from RCTs. From each registry we obtained HRs between LAI vs oral counterparts; then, we synthesized these HRs in a random-effects meta-analysis to compare the average treatment effects between the two formulations across all drugs available as LAI and oral formulations. Following suggestions of peer reviewers, we performed two additional post-hoc analyses: first, we excluded from the registries individuals diagnosed with schizoaffective disorder; second, we excluded from the registries individuals using

clozapine at baseline. We then repeated the main analysis of the registry data to verify the robustness of our conclusions when excluding these patients.

Analysis of RCT data

We used HRs to obtain similar effect measures for RW and RCTs. If original publications of RCTs provided HRs for relapse at 6-month follow-up (or 12-months for sensitivity analyses), we used those. Otherwise, we used published survival curves to estimate HRs according to established methodology³² used in several meta-analyses^{33,34} (Supplement, Section 4). Transitivity was already assessed in the original NMA.²³ For the RCT-NMA we used the same methods as for the RW-NMA (see above).

Assessing agreement between real-world data and RCT data

To compare RW and RCT findings, we created scatterplots with one axis showing relative efficacy (HR) of drugs vs oral haloperidol in RCTs and the other effectiveness in RW, including 95% CIs. To quantify RW-RCT agreement, we used HRs vs haloperidol oral to obtain RHRs (i.e., HR obtained from RW over HR from RCT), and estimated the weighted Spearman rank correlation.

Joint synthesis of real world and RCT data

If results were deemed comparable between RW and RCTs, we synthesized all evidence in NMA, using methods described above. We used placebo (in RCTs) and non-use (in RW) as different nodes in the network. To present results, we chose haloperidol oral as reference treatment given its widespread and long-standing use.

Secondary outcomes and sensitivity analyses

We used two alternative outcomes to assess the robustness of our findings. First, we analysed all-cause discontinuation (until study endpoint in RCTs). Second, we repeated analyses using 12 months of follow-up.

We performed a series of prespecified sensitivity analyses. First, we ran a sensitivity analysis by starting the follow-up for RW non-users the moment they discontinued their previous antipsychotic use (mimicking situations wherein non-users are first “stabilized” on antipsychotic monotherapy). Second, we excluded first-episode RCTs. Third, we excluded open RCTs. Fourth, we repeated analyses using rehospitalisation (until study endpoint) instead of study-defined relapse as the RCT outcome.

Ethics

Regarding the Finnish registry, this project was approved by the Finnish National Institute for Health and Welfare. Further permissions were granted by pertinent institutional authorities at this Institute, the Social Insurance Institution of Finland, and Statistics Finland. Regarding the Swedish registry, the project was approved by the regional Ethical review board in Sweden (grant numbers 2007/762-31 and 2016-1533-32). The current RW study was registry-based, and no contact was made with its participants of the study; therefore, informed consent from patients was not required. For RCT-data, ethical approval/patient consent was obtained within the context of the original studies.

Results

We included 29,637 individuals from the Swedish and 60,832 from the Finnish registry, with a total of 18,713 and 64,583 person-years, respectively. Mean age at cohort entry was 44.9 years (SD 12.0) in the Swedish and 46.4 (15.9) in the Finnish registry, with 43.0% (N=12,741) and 49.8% (30,284) being women, respectively (details in Supplement, Section 5.1). For the entire RW study population, the mean age was 45.9 (SD 14.6) years and N=43,025 (48%) were women. *Figure 2A* shows estimated effects from the two registries for all drugs vs oral haloperidol. The weighted Spearman's rank correlation for the HRs was 0.93 ($p=0.0004$). The RHR for Swedish over Finnish registry was 0.97 [0.88; 1.08]; additional statistics and graphical displays are in Supplement, Section 5.2. We deemed that the registries had comparable populations, transitivity was plausible, and we therefore conducted NMA. We found no evidence of network heterogeneity or inconsistency (Supplement, Section 5.3). Clozapine was most effective, followed by olanzapine LAI (*Figure 2B*).

Figure 2: Panel A shows relapse Hazard Ratios (HRs) vs haloperidol oral and 95% CI estimated separately from the two registries. HRs > 1 favor Haloperidol oral. Panel B shows results from a network meta-analysis (NMA) of the two registries. Drugs are ordered by decreasing effectiveness. Red color indicates oral, blue long-acting injectables (LAI). CLO: clozapine; OLA: olanzapine. ARI: aripiprazole; ZIP: ziprasidone;

HAL: haloperidol; PAL: paliperidone; RIS: risperidone; SER: sertindole; QUE: quetiapine. For each drug, 'x.L' denotes LAI and 'x.O' the oral formulation of 'x' drug.

Figure 3 shows the comparison of RW effects between RCT-eligible and RCT-ineligible individuals, for drugs vs no antipsychotic use. We observed that drug effectiveness for all drugs was larger in eligible individuals. The pooled RHR was 1.40 [1.24; 1.59] (Supplement, Section 6), i.e., drugs' effectiveness was 40% larger in RCT-eligible individuals. When comparing LAI vs oral formulations of drugs for which both were present in the RW dataset, we found evidence of superior effectiveness of LAI. The average HR across the registries for LAI vs. oral was 0.88 ([0.81; 0.95]; Supplement, Section 5.2, eFigure 6).

Figure 3: Hazard Ratios (HRs) of all drugs vs no antipsychotic use, for real world (RW) individuals who would be eligible to a standard randomized controlled trial ('RCT-eligible individuals', x-axis) and individuals who would not ('RCT-ineligible individuals', y-axis). Effectiveness was estimated via a

network meta-analysis of the Swedish and Finnish registries. Red color indicates oral, blue long-acting injectables (LAI). Drug abbreviations as per Figure 2.

From 51 studies fulfilling the inclusion criteria in terms of population and interventions, 30 RCTs (10,091 participants) analysed relapse with survival analysis and were thus usable for the primary outcome analysis (1 additional study did not provide censoring information on the survival curve and therefore was not usable). The mean age across those 30 RCTs was 39.6 years (SD 11.7), the median of mean age was 39.0 (range: 21.5 to 49.7). The mean percentage of women was 36.9%. We provide a flow chart of the selection process, descriptives of the included studies, as well as a risk of bias assessment in the Supplement, Section 2. For three trials, we obtained relapse HRs from published data. For the remaining 27 RCTs we extracted HRs from published Kaplan-Meier curves. Supplement, Section 6.4 shows results of individual studies, pairwise meta-analyses of each comparison, and a meta-analysis of five studies comparing LAI vs oral formulations of the same drug. In the latter, opposite to the finding in registries, the pooled effect favoured oral administrations, albeit with statistical uncertainty. The NMA of RCTs indicated heterogeneity ($\tau = 0.45$) and inconsistency (design-by-treatment test $p=0.004$; local method: 3 of 11 detachable comparisons showed evidence of inconsistency, Supplement, Section 5.4) and the certainty in the estimates was generally low (Supplement 5.4.4). In *Figure 4*, we show the network graph and the estimated effects vs oral haloperidol.

Figure 4: Panel A, the network of available randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Numbers indicate the number of studies performing each comparison. Panel B, estimated Hazard Ratios (HRs) for all drugs vs placebo via a network meta-analysis. Red for oral, blue for long-acting injectable (LAI).

We then compared RW and RCT effect estimates and found differences between RCTs and RW: the average ratio of HR of drug vs no antipsychotic (RW) over HR of drug vs placebo (RCTs) was 2.58 ([2.02; 3.30]; $p < 0.0001$), i.e. treatment efficacy in RCTs was on average 2.58 times larger than the drug-corresponding effectiveness in RW. However, the weighted Spearman's rank correlation was 0.59 ($p = 0.06$), indicating that treatment ranking in RCTs reflected, to some extent, ranking in RW. When comparing HRs of drugs vs haloperidol, we found the RHR to be 1.17 ([0.83; 1.65]; $p = 0.36$), i.e. almost no evidence of disagreement. Spearman's weighted correlation was 0.64 ($p = 0.04$). For most drugs, point estimates were in good agreement between RCTs and RW (Figure 5). However, for olanzapine we found discrepancies of the estimated effects, although with large statistical uncertainty. RCTs showed weak evidence favoring oral vs. equivalent LAIs (HR 1.21 [0.89; 1.63]). The RHR for the oral-LAI comparison in RW vs. RCTs was 0.73 ([0.53; 0.99]; $p = 0.04$), i.e. LAIs had superior effects in the RW to RCTs.

Figure 5: Comparison of Hazard Ratios (HRs) of all drugs vs haloperidol oral in the registries (green) vs. RCTs (grey). RW: real-world. RCT: randomized controlled trial. Only drugs found in both datasets (RW and RCTs) are shown.

We then performed a joint NMA of RCT and registry data. This NMA showed little evidence of heterogeneity ($\tau = 0.14$) and inconsistency (design-by-treatment test $p=0.40$). Precision was low for the top-ranked drugs (asenapine, iloperidone, and zotepine) and these drugs were only available in RCTs (1 trial vs placebo each; *Figure 6*). Clozapine (available only in RW)

ranked second according to p-scores (HR 0.61 [0.48; 0.77], $p < 0.0001$), combining a large effect size with high precision. Olanzapine oral (HR 0.71 [0.57; 0.88], $p = 0.002$) was present in both RCTs and RW and ranked high in the joint NMA, the RCT-NMA and RW-NMA; however, the two sources disagreed on the magnitude of the effect (*Figure 5*). Drugs with the least benefit compared to placebo/no antipsychotics (cariprazine and lurasidone) only had RCT evidence. Drugs with evidence from both registries and RCTs generally yielded more precise but less pronounced effects. In Section 7 of the Supplement we provide the PRISMA-NMA checklist.³⁵

Figure 6: Hazard Ratios (HRs) of drugs vs haloperidol oral from a network meta-analysis combining randomized and non-randomized evidence. Grey-colored drugs were only available in randomized controlled trials (RCTs). Green-colored drugs were only available in registry data. Orange-colored drugs were present in both RCT and registry data. Drugs are ranked according to their p-scores.

Finally, results from secondary outcomes and most sensitivity analyses (Supplement sections 8-13) either agreed with the main analyses or did not provide further insights, e.g. because of low precision estimates resulting from low statistical power. The sensitivity analysis

of using rehospitalisation as an outcome showed differences with the main analysis; however, this analysis suffered from limited data quality (Supplement section 13).

Discussion

We used individual patient data from two national registries and study-level information from 30 RCTs (totalling >100,000 subjects), to compare antipsychotic drugs for individuals with schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder, using relapse as the primary outcome. To the best of our knowledge, our work constitutes the largest meta-analysis of antipsychotic treatment effects and the first study synthesizing large-scale evidence from RW and RCT settings in the field of mental health.

Our RW results indicate that antipsychotic beneficial effects vs no drug use are larger in individuals *eligible* for RCTs (i.e., those meeting stringent inclusion criteria) than in *ineligible* individuals (i.e., those who are not usually represented in RCTs). Similarly, drug effects vs. placebo in RCTs were higher than effects vs. no drug use in RW. We thus triangulated a difference between RCT and RW effects. However, RCT estimates of relative effects for relapse prevention between drugs were generally in good agreement with those from registries. We therefore conclude that, although efficacy vs placebo in RCTs may not be directly portable to RW-effectiveness vs no antipsychotic use, we find no evidence of an “efficacy-effectiveness gap”³ in head-to-head antipsychotic drug comparisons.

In RW, we found LAIs to be more effective than oral formulations, in line with previous analyses of RW data using a different outcome;^{36,37} conversely, in RCTs we found weak evidence favouring oral. This discrepancy may be due to less severely ill and more adherent individuals included in RCTs than in RW, frequent follow-up visits in RCTs and/or low doses of olanzapine LAI in two of the five RCTs (Supplement, Section 6.4).³⁸ Nonetheless, in a meta-analysis with broader inclusion criteria across comparisons,¹⁷ LAI was superior to oral compounds also in RCTs.

We believe our work may inspire other areas of medicine to attempt similar integrative RW-RCT approaches, as well as serve as a basis for updating and revamping current treatment guidelines for schizophrenia. For example, except for the indication of clozapine in treatment-resistant schizophrenia, most guidelines do not list specific antipsychotics in any preferential order. We found that in RW, clozapine and LAIs performed well for relapse prevention (with olanzapine LAI outperforming other LAI formulations); in the RCT-NMA and RCT/RW-NMA olanzapine LAI also ranked very high. We thus recommend to not only consider LAIs (e.g. olanzapine) in the event of patient preference and non-adherence (as currently suggested in the American Psychiatric Association (APA) schizophrenia treatment guideline),³⁹ but also in patients with schizophrenia in general. Additionally, we fill a current knowledge gap about superiority of antipsychotics by substantiating evidence of superior effectiveness of certain antipsychotics (e.g., of olanzapine to haloperidol). Finally, as the APA schizophrenia guideline is partly based on expert opinions,³⁹ we suggest the joint assessment of RW evidence with RCTs for further development of schizophrenia treatment guidelines.

A strength of our study is the methodology used to integrate data from real-world and RCT settings. Additionally, our analyses were based on a larger study population with a more extended follow-up period than any previous studies in these registries. Moreover, the large number of individuals and the long follow-up allowed us to run within-person analysis, where each patient acted as their own control, reducing the risk of confounding. Nonetheless, limitations should be borne in mind when interpreting the results. First, there may still be unmeasured confounding in our within-individual analysis, such as due to severity or instability of symptoms (e.g., if patients in RW start or stop medication when they feel either more or less ill). However, an alternative, across-individual analysis (i.e. adjusting for confounding across patients) would likely be heavily

biased, due to lack of information on possible confounders in the registries. Confounding due to baseline severity is arguably more probable in comparisons of no antipsychotic vs. drug use, rather than between drugs, and this is perhaps why relative effects agreed between registries, as well as between RW and RCTs, in contrast to comparisons vs no use/placebo. Second, participation in RCTs may be driven not only by eligibility, but also by the individuals' willingness to participate, e.g. the presence of paranoid delusions may curtail an individual's predisposition to participate in a trial. Third, inclusion of patients with schizoaffective disorder may theoretically pose a problem, as RCTs, in contrast to RW, usually include only few such patients; however, it has been shown that there are no systematic differences in treatment effects between schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder,⁴⁰ which was further confirmed by the results of our sensitivity analyses. Fourth, due to limitations in the data reported in RCTs and in the data available for nationwide registries, we were unable to conduct some specific analyses. For example, we restricted our analyses to 6 and 12 months because this was the duration of follow up for most RCTs; however, schizophrenia affects patients for much longer durations. Similarly, we limited analyses to HRs, and thus data of 17 RCTs only reporting numbers of patients with relapses but not HRs or survival curves could not be used. Using other effect measures (e.g. risk ratios) would lead to great loss of information from the registries, due to frequent censoring before 6 months. Further, we did not do a formal appraisal of the evidence of the joint RW-RCT-NMA, e.g., using the CINeMA approach⁴¹ as this does not currently accommodate observational studies. In addition, we were unable to conduct sex/gender stratified analyses or include amisulpride in any of our analyses. We were also unable to fully harmonise definitions of the outcome and eligibility criteria so as to match RCT definitions (that also vary substantially between RCTs). Consequently, our definition of RCT-eligibility applied to the RW-individuals is even more explanatory and less pragmatic than in RCTs

(particularly because we excluded patients who had ever had a diagnosis of substance abuse or suicide attempt). Nevertheless, given that the majority of studies used for the primary outcome are registrational trials conducted by pharmaceutical companies that are designed as explanatory and not as pragmatic trials, we deem their participants largely comparable to the selected RCT-eligible patients from the RW. Fifth, one of the several sensitivity analyses we performed, i.e. using rehospitalisation as an outcome in RCTs, gave results incongruent with the primary analysis, but data quality was poor (Supplement section 13). Finally, although an NMA of RCTs was not our main focus, the RCT network was thinly connected, heterogeneous and inconsistent and thus the certainty in the estimates of this specific analysis was relatively low.

We suggest all future RCTs make IPD available, allowing for IPD meta-analyses. To optimise interpretability and utility of RCT findings, superiority trials over active comparators should be favoured, keeping placebo-controlled trials as pivotal registration studies.⁴² Furthermore, dose-specific comparative analyses between RCTs and RW may be conducted. Also, it would be interesting to apply similar approaches to different RW healthcare settings. Another research avenue is to explore the comparative tolerability of antipsychotics across RW and RCT settings, although this will likely be challenging.

In summary, except for effect differences between oral and LAI antipsychotics, we found that antipsychotic between-drug comparison findings for the outcome of relapse prevention may be portable from RCTs to the real world. Effects of antipsychotic drugs vs. placebo reported in RCTs may overestimate effects vs. no antipsychotic use observed in routine practice.

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Role funder/sponsor statement

The funders of the study had no role in the design and conduct of the study; collection, management, analysis, and interpretation of the data; preparation, review, or approval of the manuscript; and decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

Contributors

All authors conceived the study. OE, HT and JS-T curated the data. OE, HT, JR, JS-T, JPE, MO, JT and JL made the statistical analysis plan. OE, HT, JR, JS-T, and MO carried out the data analysis. AC, EV, SL, JT and JL supervised the project. OE, HT, JR, JS-T, JPE, MO, JT and JL wrote the first draft. Project management was done by JL. All co-authors were involved in the critical review and writing of the final draft that was submitted, as well as the submitted revision. HT and AT verified and had full access to all the RW-data in the study and take responsibility for the integrity of the data and the accuracy of the data analysis. JS-T, SL, MO and JR verified and had full access to the RCT-data and take responsibility for the integrity of the data. OE and HT take responsibility for data analysis. JL had the final responsibility for the decision to submit this work for publication.

Code and data availability

We provide data and code to replicate our primary analysis in the Supplement, Section 14.

Author conflict of interest disclosures

OE has received honoraria and consulting fees from Biogen to his institution, all unrelated to the current work.

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SL has received, in the last three years, honoraria as a consultant and/or advisor and/or for lectures and/or for educational material from Alkermes, Angelini, Eisai, Gedeon Richter, Janssen, Lundbeck, Medichem,

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